

ASYMPTOTIC ESTIMATES FOR PHI FUNCTIONS FOR SUBSETS OF $\{M + 1, M + 2, \dots, N\}$

Melvyn B. Nathanson¹

*Department of Mathematics, Lehman College (CUNY), Bronx, New York 10468, USA, and
School of Mathematics, Institute for Advanced Study, Princeton, NJ 08540
melvyn.nathanson@lehman.cuny.edu, melvyn@ias.edu*

Brooke Orosz

*Department of Mathematics, CUNY Graduate Center, New York, New York 10036
borosz@gc.cuny.edu*

Received: 9/15/07, Accepted: 11/12/07, Published: 12/5/07

Abstract

Let $f(m, n)$ denote the number of relatively prime subsets of $\{m + 1, m + 2, \dots, n\}$, and let $\Phi(m, n)$ denote the number of subsets A of $\{m + 1, m + 2, \dots, n\}$ such that $\gcd(A)$ is relatively prime to n . Let $f_k(m, n)$ and $\Phi_k(m, n)$ be the analogous counting functions restricted to sets of cardinality k . Simple explicit formulas and asymptotic estimates are obtained for these four functions.

A nonempty set A of integers is called *relatively prime* if $\gcd(A) = 1$. Let $f(n)$ denote the number of nonempty relatively prime subsets of $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and, for $k \geq 1$, let $f_k(n)$ denote the number of relatively prime subsets of $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ of cardinality k .

Euler's phi function $\varphi(n)$ counts the number of positive integers a in the set $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ such that a is relatively prime to n . The Phi function $\Phi(n)$ counts the number of nonempty subsets A of the set $\{1, \dots, n\}$ such that $\gcd(A)$ is relatively prime to n or, equivalently, such that $A \cup \{n\}$ is relatively prime. For every positive integer k , the function $\Phi_k(n)$ counts the number of sets $A \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that $\text{card}(A) = k$ and $\gcd(A)$ is relatively prime to n .

Nathanson [2] introduced these four functions for subsets of $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, and El Bachraoui [1] generalized them to subsets of the set $\{m + 1, m + 2, \dots, n\}$ for arbitrary nonnegative integers $m < n$.² We shall obtain simple explicit formulas and asymptotic estimates for the four functions.

¹The work of M.B.N. was supported in part by grants from the NSA Mathematical Sciences Program and the PSC-CUNY Research Award Program.

²Actually, our function $f(m, n)$ is El Bachraoui's function $f(m + 1, n)$, and similarly for the other three functions. This small change yields formulas that are more symmetric and pleasing esthetically.

For every real number x , we denote by $[x]$ the greatest integer not exceeding x . We often use the elementary inequality $[x] - [y] \leq [x - y] + 1$ for all $x, y \in \mathbf{R}$.

Theorem 1. For nonnegative integers $m < n$, let $f(m, n)$ denote the number of relatively prime subsets of $\{m + 1, m + 2, \dots, n\}$. Then

$$f(m, n) = \sum_{d=1}^n \mu(d) (2^{\lfloor n/d \rfloor - \lfloor m/d \rfloor} - 1)$$

and $0 \leq 2^{n-m} - 2^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor - \lfloor m/2 \rfloor} - f(m, n) \leq 2n2^{\lfloor (n-m)/3 \rfloor}$.

Proof. El Bachraoui [1] proved that

$$f(m, n) = \sum_{d=1}^n \mu(d) (2^{\lfloor n/d \rfloor} - 1) - \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{d|i} \mu(d) 2^{\lfloor n/d \rfloor - i/d}.$$

Rearranging this identity, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} f(m, n) &= \sum_{d=1}^n \mu(d) (2^{\lfloor n/d \rfloor} - 1) - \sum_{d=1}^m \mu(d) 2^{\lfloor n/d \rfloor} \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ d|i}}^m 2^{-i/d} \\ &= \sum_{d=1}^n \mu(d) (2^{\lfloor n/d \rfloor} - 1) - \sum_{d=1}^m \mu(d) 2^{\lfloor n/d \rfloor} \sum_{j=1}^{\lfloor m/d \rfloor} 2^{-j} \\ &= \sum_{d=1}^n \mu(d) 2^{\lfloor n/d \rfloor} \left(1 - \sum_{j=1}^{\lfloor m/d \rfloor} 2^{-j} \right) - \sum_{d=1}^n \mu(d) \\ &= \sum_{d=1}^n \mu(d) (2^{\lfloor n/d \rfloor - \lfloor m/d \rfloor} - 1). \end{aligned}$$

Let $d \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Then $m + 1 \leq a \leq n$ and d divides a if and only if $\lfloor m/d \rfloor + 1 \leq a/d \leq \lfloor n/d \rfloor$. It follows that $A \subseteq \{m + 1, \dots, n\}$ and $\gcd(A) = d$ if and only if $A' = (1/d) * A \subseteq \{\lfloor m/d \rfloor + 1, \dots, \lfloor n/d \rfloor\}$ and $\gcd(A') = 1$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} 2^{n-m} - 1 &= \sum_{d=1}^n f(\lfloor m/d \rfloor, \lfloor n/d \rfloor) \\ &\leq f(m, n) + 2^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor - \lfloor m/2 \rfloor} - 1 + \sum_{d=3}^n 2^{\lfloor n/d \rfloor - \lfloor m/d \rfloor} \end{aligned}$$

and we obtain the lower bound $f(m, n) \geq 2^{n-m} - 2^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor - \lfloor m/2 \rfloor} - 2n2^{\lfloor (n-m)/3 \rfloor}$. For the upper bound, we observe that the number of subsets of even integers contained in $\{m + 1, \dots, n\}$ is exactly $2^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor - \lfloor m/2 \rfloor}$ and so $f(m, n) \leq 2^{n-m} - 2^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor - \lfloor m/2 \rfloor}$. This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 2. For nonnegative integers $m < n$ and for $k \geq 1$, let $f_k(m, n)$ denote the number of relatively prime subsets of $\{m + 1, m + 2, \dots, n\}$ of cardinality k . Then

$$f_k(m, n) = \sum_{d=1}^n \mu(d) \binom{[n/d] - [m/d]}{k}$$

and

$$0 \leq \binom{n - m}{k} - \binom{[n/2] - [m/2]}{k} - f_k(m, n) \leq n \binom{[(n - m)/3] + 2}{k}.$$

Proof. El Bachraoui [1] proved that

$$f_k(m, n) = \sum_{d=1}^n \mu(d) \binom{[n/d]}{k} - \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{d|i} \mu(d) \binom{[n/d] - i/d}{k - 1}.$$

We recall the combinatorial fact that for $k \geq 1$ and $0 \leq M \leq N$, we have

$$\binom{N}{k} - \sum_{j=1}^M \binom{N - j}{k - 1} = \binom{N - M}{k}.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} f_k(m, n) &= \sum_{d=1}^n \mu(d) \binom{[n/d]}{k} - \sum_{d=1}^m \mu(d) \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ d|i}}^m \binom{[n/d] - i/d}{k - 1} \\ &= \sum_{d=1}^m \mu(d) \left(\binom{[n/d]}{k} - \sum_{j=1}^{[m/d]} \binom{[n/d] - j}{k - 1} \right) + \sum_{d=m+1}^n \mu(d) \binom{[n/d]}{k} \\ &= \sum_{d=1}^m \mu(d) \binom{[n/d] - [m/d]}{k} + \sum_{d=m+1}^n \mu(d) \binom{[n/d]}{k} \\ &= \sum_{d=1}^n \mu(d) \binom{[n/d] - [m/d]}{k}. \end{aligned}$$

We obtain an upper bound for $f_k(m, n)$ by deleting k -element sets of even integers:

$$f_k(m, n) \leq \binom{n - m}{k} - \binom{[n/2] - [m/2]}{k}$$

and we obtain a lower bound from the identity

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{n - m}{k} &= \sum_{d=1}^n f_k([m/d], [n/d]) \\ &\leq f_k(m, n) + \binom{[n/2] - [m/2]}{k} + \sum_{d=3}^n \binom{[n/d] - [m/d]}{k} \\ &\leq f_k(m, n) + \binom{[n/2] - [m/2]}{k} + n \binom{[(n - m)/3]}{k}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 3. For nonnegative integers $m < n$, let $\Phi(m, n)$ denote the number of subsets of $[m + 1, n]$ such that $\gcd(A)$ is relatively prime to n . Then

$$\Phi(m, n) = \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) 2^{(n/d) - [m/d]}.$$

If p^* is the smallest prime divisor of n , then

$$0 \leq 2^{n-m} - 2^{(n/p^*) - [m/p^*]} - \Phi(m, n) \leq 2n 2^{[(n-m)/(p^*+1)]}.$$

Proof. El Bachraoui [1] proved that

$$\Phi(m, n) = \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) 2^{n/d} - \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{d|(i,n)} \mu(d) 2^{(n-i)/d}$$

Rearranging this identity, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(m, n) &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) 2^{n/d} - \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ d|i}}^m 2^{(n-i)/d} \\ &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) 2^{n/d} - \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \sum_{j=1}^{[m/d]} 2^{(n-jd)/d} \\ &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) 2^{n/d} \left[1 - \sum_{j=1}^{[m/d]} 2^{-j} \right] \\ &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) 2^{(n/d) - [m/d]}. \end{aligned}$$

Let p^* be the smallest prime divisor of n . Deleting all subsets of $\{m + 1, \dots, n\}$ whose elements are all multiples of p^* , we obtain the upper bound

$$\Phi(m, n) \leq 2^{n-m} - 2^{(n/p^*) - [m/p^*]}.$$

For the lower bound, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(m, n) - (2^{n-m} - 2^{(n/p^*) - [m/p^*]}) &= \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d > p^*}} \mu(d) 2^{(n/d) - [m/d]} \\ &\leq 2 \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d > p^*}} 2^{[(n-m)/d]} \leq 2n 2^{[(n-m)/(p^*+1)]}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

Theorem 4. For nonnegative integers $m < n$, let $\Phi_k(m, n)$ denote the number of subsets of cardinality k contained in the interval of integers $\{m + 1, m + 2, \dots, n\}$ such that $\gcd(A)$ is relatively prime to n . Then

$$\Phi_k(m, n) = \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \binom{n/d - [m/d]}{k}$$

and

$$0 \leq \binom{n-m}{k} - \binom{n/p^* - [m/p^*]}{k} - \Phi_k(m, n) \leq n \binom{[(n-m)/(p^*+1)] + 1}{k}.$$

Proof. Let p^* be the smallest prime divisor of n . El Bachraoui [1] proved that

$$\Phi_k(m, n) = \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \binom{n/d}{k} - \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{d|\gcd(i,n)} \mu(d) \binom{(n-i)/d}{k-1}.$$

Rearranging this identity, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_k(m, n) &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \binom{n/d}{k} - \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ d|i}}^m \binom{(n-i)/d}{k-1} \\ &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \left(\binom{n/d}{k} - \sum_{j=1}^{[m/d]} \binom{n/d-j}{k-1} \right) \\ &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \binom{n/d - [m/d]}{k} \\ &\geq \binom{n-m}{k} - \binom{n/p^* - [m/p^*]}{k} - \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d > p^*}} \binom{n/d - [m/d]}{k} \\ &\geq \binom{n-m}{k} - \binom{n/p^* - [m/p^*]}{k} - \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d > p^*}} \binom{[(n-m)/d] + 1}{k} \\ &\geq \binom{n-m}{k} - \binom{n/p^* - [m/p^*]}{k} - n \binom{[(n-m)/(p^*+1)] + 1}{k}. \end{aligned}$$

Deleting k -element subsets of $\{m+1, \dots, n\}$ whose elements are multiples of p^* , we get the upper bound

$$\Phi_k(m, n) \leq \binom{n-m}{k} - \binom{[n/p^*] - [m/p^*]}{k}.$$

This completes the proof. □

References

- [1] M. El Bachraoui, *The number of relatively prime subsets and phi functions for $\{m, m+1, \dots, n\}$* , Integers **7** (2007), A43, 8 pp. (electronic).
- [2] M. B. Nathanson, *Affine invariants, relatively prime sets, and a phi function for subsets of $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$* , Integers **7** (2007), A1, 7 pp. (electronic).